

Variation of the Charge of Colloidal Particles with Concentrations of Electrolytes.

Part I.

Arsenious Sulphide Sol and Acids

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The stability of most colloidal solutions of inorganic substances is intimately connected with its electric charge. We believe that the potential of the double layer is one out of several factors which determine the rate of precipitation (*cf.* Mukherjee and Sen, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1919, 115, 466; Mukherjee, *ibid.*, 1920, 117, 356; and Papaconstantinou, *ibid.*, 1920, 117, 1566; Mukherjee and Majumdar, *ibid.*, 1924, 125, 791). One of us has suggested that the narrowness of the range of precipitating concentrations is to be sought for in the great effect, which a small diminution of the potential of the double layer has on the percentage of successful collisions between the particles, which lead to their coalescence (Mukherjee, *Thesis*, 1921, also Mukherjee and Majumdar, *loc. cit.*). When two particles come near each other, the mutual electrical forces disturb the distribution of the ions composing the mobile sheet of the double layer and a new arrangement results. The displacement of these ions that takes place requires the expenditure of work against electrical forces at the expense of the kinetic energy of approach of the colliding particles. The stabilising effect of the electrical double

layer is to be attributed to this energy change. It is well-known that cohesive forces decrease much more rapidly with distance than electrical forces and it is only when the particles are sufficiently near each other that they predominate over the electrical forces. The fraction of the total number of collisions which is successful in bringing about coalescence, would therefore be dependent on the magnitude of the cohesive forces¹ and on the change in the electrical energy associated with such coalescence. *The electrical work will evidently depend on the number of ions which suffer a shift in their position, on the changes in their positions with respect to the colloidal particles and on the dielectric constant of the medium.* The number of displaceable charges determines the density of the free electrical charge of the colloidal particle. Thus we see that other things remaining unaltered, as the free charge on the surface of the colloid decreases the electrical work referred to above also diminishes. Though investigations on the coagulation of colloids under different conditions are numerous, determinations of electrical charge under these conditions are seldom made. In most papers in discussing the experimental results, one or more of the following assumptions are usually made:—

(1) The electrical charge of the colloid does not vary on dilution. If there is a diminution of the charge with dilution, the discussion of results and the conclusions drawn therefrom lose much of their force, and in some cases they are to be completely revised (*cf.* Mukherjee and Chaudhuri, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 125, 801).

(2) Coagulation takes place at the iso-electric point.

¹ It is also quite possible that when the particles are not exactly spherical, relative positions of the two particles might mean a difference in the magnitude of the cohesive forces, which are brought into play.

(3) The electrical charge (or the potential of the double layer) on the particles of a colloid is identical for concentrations of different electrolytes which produce the same rate of coagulation.

No data are, however, given to support such assumptions. The absence of such determinations is in part to be ascribed to the difficulties in making reliable and accurate determinations of the charge. In the present paper the data obtained on the influence of acids on the electrical charge of arsenious sulphide hydrosols prepared under different conditions are recorded, and the results have been discussed from the theoretical point of view.

EXPERIMENTAL.

A.—*Method of Measuring the Charge.*

The method, described by one of us (Mukherjee, *Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1923, 103, 102), has been found to give reliable and accurate values for the velocity of migration. *What we actually measure is the velocity of the colloidal particles under unit potential gradient.* Without further assumptions it is not possible to assign a definite value either to the electric charge on the particles or the potential of the double layer surrounding them. A variation in the velocity may be taken to indicate a proportionate variation in the density of the electrical charge (*cf.* Lamb, Smoluchowski, *vide supra*). The apparatus, previously described, has been slightly modified. The distance between the side tubes has been increased to 2 cm. In course of the large number of measurements we have made, we had occasion to examine more closely other sources of error which were not referred to in the earlier paper (Mukherjee, *loc. cit.*). We have found that the heating effect of the electric current is negligible unless the potential gradient and the specific conductivity of

the liquid are very great. The viscosity of the medium in which the particle moves ought to be measured. In the present instance the variations in viscosity are negligible compared to the error involved in reading the movement of the boundary. Electrolysis during the measurement is a greater source of error and care ought to be taken to use not very high potential gradients or prolong the movement too long. *It is of utmost importance to determine the potential gradient before and after the movement and to secure a minimum variation in its value.* For in case of large changes in the potential gradient during the movement, there is an obvious error in calculating the velocity per unit potential gradient unless we also know accurately the variation in the potential gradient continuously with time during the movement of the boundary. For these reasons we do not think it desirable to simplify the procedure as has been done by Freundlich and Zeh (*Z. physical. Chem.*, 1924, 114, 65).

B.—*Preparation of Arsenious Sulphide Sols.*

The sols were prepared in several ways as follows:

(1) Equal volumes of water saturated with hydrogen sulphide and doubly diluted saturated solution of arsenious acid were mixed. The resulting mixture was divided into two portions. Through one portion pure hydrogen sulphide was bubbled for one hour (sol A). Through the other portion pure hydrogen was passed till there was no smell of the sulphuretted hydrogen, *i.e.*, into this portion, hydrogen sulphide was not passed at all after the mixing (sol B). A portion of sol B was coagulated and when hydrogen sulphide was passed into the clear decanted liquid, arsenious sulphide was precipitated, showing the presence of free arsenious acid in the sol. The results with these sols are given in Table I.

(2) The colloid was prepared by mixing equal volumes of water saturated with hydrogen sulphide and doubly diluted saturated solution of arsenious acid, and then by passing hydrogen sulphide to saturation. The hydrogen sulphide was then driven off by pure hydrogen (sol C). A portion of this colloid was taken and saturated with hydrogen sulphide when required on the day of the experiment. The water or the acid used was also saturated with hydrogen sulphide (sol D). The results are given in Table II. The results with H_2SO_4 were obtained with a different sol prepared as in the case of sol C (sol C').

(3) Equal volumes of water saturated with hydrogen sulphide and 4 times diluted saturated solution of arsenious acid were quickly mixed and thoroughly shaken and hydrogen sulphide and then hydrogen were passed as usual (sol E). The results are given in Table III.

In the following tables v , stands for the velocity of migration of the colloid-electrolyte boundary in cm. per sec. per volt per cm.; C , stands for concentration of the electrolyte in gm. equivalents per litre and C_H ,* for hydrogen ion concentration at 18° .

TABLE I

Arsenious Sulphide Sol and Hydrochloric Acid.

Concentration (C)	Rate of migration (v)	
	Sol A	Sol B
0	48.6	62.9
0.00033	52.0	—
0.001	56.1	54.0
0.002	51.7	47.0
0.004	52.5	45.0
0.01	58.1	44.3

* Calculations of hydrogen ion concentrations of the weak acids have been made from data on conductivity (*vide* Kohlrausch, *Leitvermögen der Elektrolyte*).

TABLE II
Arsenious Sulphide.

Concentration (C)	Rate of migration (v)		
	Sol C' and HCl	Sol D and HCl	Sol C' and H ₂ SO ₄
0	53.2	59.4	71.8
0.00038	44.3	52.3	60.9
0.00086	—	—	57.0
0.001	41.7	48.8	—
0.002	45.1	43.5	—
0.004	45.9	42.8	54.5

DISCUSSION OF RESULTS.

A.—*Irregular Variation of the Charge with Acids.*

It will be seen from Table I that sol A shows a complicated variation of the velocity with the concentration, whereas a simpler variation was observed with sol B. Sol B differed from sol A in being free from hydrogen sulphide and also contained an appreciable quantity of free arsenious acid. Freundlich and Nathansohn (*Koll. Zeit.*, 1921, 28, 258) have suggested that the free hydrogen sulphide present in arsenious sulphide sols is photochemically oxidised to sulphur dioxide which again reacts with hydrogen sulphide to form pentathionic acid and sulphur. This sulphur adsorbs polythionate ions and thus passes into the colloidal state. In a recent paper Murphy and Mathews (*J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 45, 16) mention that the assumption of the presence of polythionic acids is necessary to explain the increase in conductivity of the sol on exposure to light. Bhatnagar and Lakshan Rao have also shown in an interesting study (*Koll. Zeit.*, 1923, 33, 164) that the transformation of the colour of orange sols of arsenious sulphide into yellow is due to the oxidation of the particles.

It may therefore be suggested that the observed complicated nature of the variation in the charge in the presence of free H_2S might be the result of several complicated reactions, namely,

(1) Interaction between hydrogen ions and anions of polythionic acids and of hydrogen sulphide in the adsorbed layer and in the solution.

(2) The change in the composition of the colloidal particles due to the formation of sulphur by reaction between polythionate ions and hydrogen ions.

We would like to draw attention to the results with sol D which shows a simpler variation. Here hydrogen sulphide was passed into the sol on the day of the experiment. It seems probable, therefore, that the mere presence of hydrogen sulphide does not produce the above-mentioned complicated variation in the charge. The sols which show a complicated variation are those which have remained in contact with hydrogen sulphide for sometime. On the other hand, sols containing free arsenious acids or which have been in contact with hydrogen sulphide for a short interval of time (12 hours), show a much simpler behaviour. We are, therefore, inclined to believe that the complicated behaviour is due to interaction between hydrogen ions and anions of polythionic acids and that the anions of hydrogen sulphide are not responsible for it. The effect of time is also intelligible as the formation of polythionic acids from the oxidation of hydrogen sulphide in solution requires time. *We would therefore conclude that sols formed in a medium containing arsenious acid in excess owe their charge practically to the adsorption of the anions of hydrogen sulphide, whereas the charge on the others is the result of the primary adsorption of anions of hydrogen sulphide and probably also of the anions of polythionic acids.*

B.—*Comparison of different Acids regarding their Effect on the Charge.*

Since the presence of free hydrogen sulphide would lead to the formation of thionic acids (and of sulphur) which, as we have just seen, would react with hydrogen ions, it was decided to compare the effect of different acids on the sols whose particles had a simpler composition. Sol E shows a simpler variation of the charge with the concentration of acid. It was prepared under conditions so that there was an excess of arsenious acid. In our previous work most of the experiments on coagulation were carried on with such sols.

TABLE III

Sol E.

Hydrochloric acid			Oxalic acid			Formic acid		
<i>C</i>	<i>v</i>	CH	<i>C</i>	<i>v</i>	CH	<i>C</i>	<i>v</i>	CH
0	68.0	—	0	68.0	—	0	68.0	—
0.005	52.6	0.0048	0.033	47.6	0.0122	0.02	45.2	0.00244
0.02	45.4	0.019	0.05	41.8	0.0175	0.05	42.2	0.00305
0.025	45.8	0.024	0.088	38.6	0.0265	0.088	37.9	0.0046
0.033	45.0	0.031	0.111	36.3	0.0333	0.443	37.2	
						2.46	34.7	0.027

SOL E AND ACETIC ACID.

<i>C</i>	<i>v</i>	CH
0	68.0	—
0.011	51.3	0.00045
0.1	35.7	0.0012

It is rather unexpected to observe in Table III that acetic and formic acids at the same hydrogen ion concentration have lowered the rate of migration, that is, the density of the electrical charge, to a greater extent than hydrochloric and oxalic acids.

Mukherjee and Chaudhuri found that a concentration of 10 normal acetic acid fails to coagulate arsenious sulphide sols. Freundlich (*Kapillarchemie*, 1922) has pointed out that the lower coagulating power of salts of organic acids is to be attributed to the adsorption of anions. One would expect that on account of the adsorption of anions in presence of acetic acid, the negative electrical charge will have a greater value than in the presence of hydrochloric acid of the same hydrogen ion concentration. The fact that acetic acid fails to coagulate arsenious sulphide sols *apparently* seems to confirm this conclusion. But the actual facts completely contradict this interpretation. We see that, contrary to our expectations, acetic acid has a greater capacity to diminish the charge than hydrochloric acid. Obviously the rate of migration alone does not determine the rate of coagulation. Apart from the relationship between the charge and the rate of coagulation, the data given in the above table confront us with another significant difficulty, namely, how to account for the greater effect of acetic and formic acids on the electrical charge of the particles. It is not infrequently that mention is made of the independent adsorption of ions meaning thereby that the adsorbability of an ion of one kind is independent of the nature of other ions present in the liquid. It is not possible to account for the peculiarities just mentioned from this point of view, unless we assume that the order of adsorbability of anions is as follows :—

Chloride > Oxalate > Formate > Acetate.

This order is the reverse of what one finds in coagulation

experiments (Mukherjee and Chaudhuri, *loc. cit.*). For those who believe in the independent adsorption of ions irrespective of the role of electrostatic forces, the only possible way out of this difficulty would lie in the assumption that electrical charge of colloidal particles has nothing to do with the adsorption of ions. Otherwise, as we have just seen, we arrive at conclusions which contradict each other. It might be suggested that neutral molecules of these acids are adsorbable to a greater extent than the anions which are present on the surface and have imparted a charge to it with the result that these *neutral* molecules displace them from the surface and lower the charge. *Against this point of view* lies the fact that such an assumption should lead us to expect a lowering of the stability of the colloid; alternatively, the facts can be explained by assuming that such an adsorption increases the stability of the sol, though it decreases the charge.

The lower rate of migration observed with these acids cannot be accounted for on the ground of the change of viscosity as the colloid-acetic acid and the colloid-hydrochloric acid mixtures show only slight difference in this respect (about 3 per cent.).

Oxalic acid shows a more complicated behaviour. Below a certain hydrogen ion concentration, the negative charge is greater in the case of oxalic than in the case of hydrochloric acid. Above it the reverse takes place. Here also a lower charge corresponds to a greater stability as the coagulating power of oxalic acid is lower than that of hydrochloric acid. The sols with which Mukherjee and Chaudhuri worked contained free arsenious acid and for reasons given in an earlier part of this work, the absence of polythionic acids is to be assumed. So the peculiarities cannot be referred to the interaction between polythionic acids and hydrogen ions.

A simple explanation, however, suggests to ourselves from the point of view that the adsorption of ions is not independent, but that a surface, which owes its charge to the adsorption of anions, can as a result of electrostatic forces take up oppositely charged ions by 'electrical adsorption' as defined by one of us. If the surface exerts no chemical affinity on the oppositely charged ion, then the electrical forces determine its adsorbability. In a previous paper (*Trans. Far. Soc., loc. cit.*) the electrical adsorbability of an oppositely charged ion was stated to be determined by w , the electrical work necessary to separate it from the surface.

$$w = \frac{n_1 n_2 E^2}{xD}$$

where n_1 is the valency of the primarily adsorbed ion and n_2 that of the oppositely charged ion; E is the electronic charge, x , the distance separating the centres of the two ions and D , the dielectric constant.

We have reasons to believe that in a large number of cases, oppositely charged ions are adsorbed on the surface in a solvated condition as opposed to what might be called adsorption of *anhydrous* ions. If, therefore, n_1 , n_2 and x remain constant, the adsorbability of the ion will increase, as the dielectric constant decreases. The cataphoretic velocities according to Helmholtz and Lamb are given by the following equations:

$$V = \frac{k(\phi_i - \phi_o)}{4\pi\eta} \quad \dots \text{ Helmholtz}$$

$$V = \frac{k(\phi_i - \phi_o)}{4\pi\eta} \times \frac{l}{d} \quad \dots \text{ Lamb}$$

The potential of the double layer ($\phi_i - \phi_o$) is directly proportional to the density of electrical charge and

inversely proportional to the dielectric constant. According to both equations the cataphoretic velocity per unit potential gradient is proportional to the density of the electrical charge on the surface and is independent of the dielectric constant of the medium (assuming l/d to be constant in the Lamb equation).

Our conception regarding electrical adsorption leads us to expect that, other factors remaining constant, the velocity of the migration for the same hydrogen ion concentration (activity) will be smaller, the lower the dielectric constant.

Now acetic and formic acids in the pure state have dielectric constants 9.7 and 58.5 at 18° and 16° respectively (Landolt-Börnstein, *Physikalisch Chemische Tabellen*, p. 1218). It is quite reasonable to assume that solutions of acetic acid or formic acid containing a fair proportion of undissociated acetic or formic acid molecules will have a dielectric constant lower than water. Unfortunately there are no data on this point. Moreover a diminution in the dielectric constant can account for the increased stability of the sol against precipitation by electrolytes. In the foregoing pages we have said that the percentage of successful collisions depend on the work against electrical forces associated with coalescence. Other things remaining constant if the dielectric constant diminishes, the electrical work involved in the displacement of electrical charges will also increase. The percentage of successful collisions will diminish rapidly in view of the exponential relations between the electrical work and the rate of coalescence (Mukherjee and Mazumdar, *loc. cit.*).

The diminution of the dielectric constant in the medium would therefore produce two effects—one tending to diminish and the other to increase the stability against precipitation by electrolytes. It is possible to conceive

that the net result in some cases will be an increase and in other cases a diminution in stability. We have made some observations in support of this statement.

The influence of the dielectric constant which we have just discussed does not preclude an actual increase in the negative charge at low concentrations of an acid owing to the adsorption of its anions (as has been suggested by Freundlich) if the dielectric constant of the medium is not much different from that of pure water. Probably some such thing happens in the case of oxalic acid; at low concentrations the number of undissociated molecules is less and the dielectric constant is not probably much different from that of water and so we observe an increase in the migration velocity from the adsorption of anions.

In conclusion we would state that the explanation we have advanced is the only one that suggests to us and can account for all of our observations. At the same time we recognise that to substantiate it, further experiments are necessary. Such experiments are in progress.

Summary.

(1) The variation of the charge of colloidal arsenious sulphide with different concentrations of various acids depends on the nature and the method of the preparation of the sols.

(2) A simple behaviour is exhibited only by those sols which contain arsenious acid in excess. The irregularities observed are probably to be attributed to an interaction between polythionic acids and hydrogen ions present in the sols.

(3) For the same hydrogen ion concentration (activity) acetic and formic acids lower the charge to a

greater extent than oxalic and hydrochloric acids. The explanation is advanced that due to the lower dielectric constants of acetic and formic acids, electrical adsorbability as defined by one of the authors increases and the charge correspondingly decreases.

(4) It has been observed that though acetic and formic acids lower the charge to a greater extent than hydrochloric acid, the coagulating power of the latter is greater and the order of coagulating power is the reverse of the order of the capacity to diminish the charge. This fact is also explained as the result of the diminution of the dielectric constant.

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Received, August 25, 1925.
